

**Impact of new generation insecticides against mustard saw fly
(*Athalia lugens proxima*) of mustard crop in Rabi season**

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ISSN: 1542-2666

NAAS Rating (2025): 5.00

<https://www.jarvm.co/index.html>

jarvm.submit@gmail.com

2025; 20-2(Part-A): 1-13

Received: 21-09-25

Accepted: 14-10-2025

Published: 29-10-2025

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17470713

Abstract:

Present investigation deals with the seasonal incidence of mustard saw fly (*Athalia lugens proxima*) and their management through various insecticides and their correlation with weather parameters. Result of seasonal incidence showed that the first appearance (0.65 grub/plant) of mustard sawfly was observed at early seedling stage (i.e. 46th SMW) of the plant, and the highest incidence was observed at 49th SMW i.e. 3rd week of November (9.6 grub/plant). Corelation study of mustard saw fly population with weather variable showed negative non-significant correlation with morning relative humidity ($r = -0.0055$) and positive non-significant correlation with evening relative humidity ($r = 0.0348$). Whereas, the negative correlation was found with minimum temperature and positive and non-significant corelation was found with maximum temperature ($r = -0.241$ & 0.0231), and rainfall ($r = 0.0294$) with mustard saw fly. For the management of mustard saw fly seven different insecticides were taken (in Plot T1) *Beauveria bassiana* 1.15% WP was taken, (in plot T2) Cyantraniliprole 10.26 OD, (in plot T3) Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC, (T4) Lambda Cyhalothrin 2.5% EC, (in plot T5) Flubendiamide 20 WG, (in plot T6) Spinetoram 11.7% SC, (in plot T7) Emamectin benzoate 5%SG was taken with control plot (T8). Among all the treatment it was found that Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC was found to be most effective insecticide with minimum saw fly population (0.40 grub/plant) and *Beauveria bassiana* 1.5% WP was found lowest effectiveness against saw fly population (1.30 grub/plant). The highest cost benefit ratio was found with Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC @ 200 ml/ha (1:3.47). Hence it can be concluded from the present study that Chlorantraniliprole could be used as effective management tool in IPM programme with increasing economy of farmers.

Keywords: *Athalia lugens proxima*, Insecticides, Mustard, mustard saw fly, ,Weather parameters

Introduction:

Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea* L.) belongs to the family *Brassicaceae* originated from China. India is the second largest producer of mustard in the world (Singh *et al.*, 2018). Rapeseed & mustard (*Brassica spp.*) is cultivated throughout India in spite of diverse agro-climatic conditions ranging from north-eastern/north-western hills to down south under irrigated/rainfed, timely/late sown, saline soils and mixed cropping over an area of 5.96 million hectare with a production of 8.32 million tones and productivity of 1397 kg/ha in 2022-23 in India. Assam records 0.29 million hectare of area with an annual production of 0.19 million tones which gives an annual yield about 669 kg/ha (Anonymous, 2023). It is the second most important edible oilseed after groundnut sharing 27.8% in the India's oilseed economy. (Pippal *et al.*, 2022). The share of oilseeds is 14.1% out of the total cropped area in India. Rapeseed-mustard is a most important edible oilseed crop in Northern India. In India rapeseed-mustard was grown during *Rabi* season under rain-fed as well as irrigated areas (Panday *et al.*, 2023). Mustard oil is one of the healthiest edible oils and is also rich in minerals like Calcium, Manganese, Copper, Iron, Selenium, Zinc, Vitamin (A, B and C) and proteins (Daravath *et al.*, 2016). Protein (28-36%), oil (28- 32 %), and essential amino acids (oleic acid, 20-28 %), linolenic acid, (10- 20 %), and erucic acid, 10-20%) are all abundant in mustard seeds (30-40 percent) (Solvane and Pathak 2016). More than 43 species of insect pests have been reported to infest rapeseed-mustard crop in India, among them sawfly (*Athalia lugens proxima*), aphid (*Lipaphis erysimi*), painted bug (*Bagrada hilaris*) and leaf miner (*Phytomyza horticola*) are the important ones (Shaila *et al.* 2022). *Athalia lugens proxima* (order: Hymenoptera: Family:Tenthredinidae) is one of the most devastating insect pests of mustard crop. The damage caused by this pest was from 3.4 to 38% during seedling stage and yield losses in mustard crop was 5 to 18 % by this pest (Dhaka

et al.; 2020). The larva alone is the most destructive stage and feeds on the margin of the leaves towards the centre. The later instars make holes, preferably on the younger leaves, and skeletonize them. Sometimes they also feed on the epidermis of the tender shoots, flowers and fruits (Chauhan and Shukla, 2014). According to Vijay Kumar *et al.* (2023), the peak activity of this pest was observed on the crop when it is in the seedling stage (Dhaka *et al.*; 2020). So, management of this pest is very necessary for increasing the yield of mustard crop and it can be tackled by using bio as well as chemical insecticides. So present study deals with seasonal incidence of mustard saw fly and their correlation with weather parameters and their effective management by using various group of insecticides. In this study bio-pesticides as well as synthetic/chemical insecticides have been used for comparative study in between them for effectiveness.

Materials and Methods:

The experiment was conducted during *Rabi* Season.

Location of the experimental site: Field experiment was carried out at the Entomology Research field situated at Diksha Bhawan, Institute of Agriculture and Natural Sciences. Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gorakhpur University Gorakhpur, during *Rabi* season in the year 2024-25. Gorakhpur is situated in the eastern part of Uttar Pradesh. This is located at 26.74 * North (Latitude) and 83.38* East (Longitude) with an altitude of 75 meters above the mean sea level.

Preparation of experimental field: Mustard was grown in the experimental field which was uniform with sandy loam soil and medium fertility. The land was given pre sowing irrigation. It was prepared by using plough followed by a subsequent harrowing. Sowing of mustard variety i.e. (Aravali) were grown in Randomized Block Design (RBD) at an experimental area in line as per agronomical

recommendation in 10 rows with 30 cm (row to row) distance. The recommended amounts of fertilizers was given in the field as required. All the agronomical practices were followed to raise a crop.

Showing time: Mustard seed was sown on 28 October 2024 in RBD design in seven plots as T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, T6, T7 and T8. Numbers of plots was 7 with three replication and one control plot which was without ant treatment. Single plot size was 3m x 3m.

Detail of the insecticides:

Plots	Detail of insecticidal treatment (plot wise) Dose/ha	Dose/ha
T1	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> 1.15% WP	5 kg/ha
T2	Cytraniliprole 10.26 OD	150 ml/ha
T3	Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC	200 ml
T4	Lambda Cyhalothrin 2.5% EC	500 ml
T5	Flubendiamide 20 WG	100 ml
T6	Spinetoram 11.7% SC	200 ml
T7	Emamectin benzoate 5% SG	200 ml
T8	Control	-

Application of insecticidal treatment:

Regular records of the seasonal occurrence of *A. proxima* were made in order to take management decision. Insecticides were firstly sprayed at ETL level of mustard saw fly i.e. 1 grub/plant comes in all plots except control plots (no any treatment).

Spraying schedule: Two-time spray was given in the experimental field, first spray was given at ETL and second spray was given after 15th days of first spray by knapsack sprayer.

Method of observation of mustard Saw fly: Mustard saw fly population was regularly observed on 5 randomly selected plant/plot at weekly interval starting germination to pre harvesting of the crop in terms of number. For seasonal incidence of mustard saw fly, five

plants from each plot were selected and sawfly larvae were counted on the 5 randomly selected plants from each field and recorded. The commencement of mustard saw fly was related with different weather conditions prevalent during crop season. The metrological data during *Rabi* 2024-25 was obtained from the Indian metrological department observatory station of Gorakhpur. The correlation between mustard saw fly and abiotic factors such as maximum temperature, minimum temperature, relative humidity morning and evening and rain fall were also observed by formula given below-

$$r = \frac{\text{Cov}(X,Y)}{\sigma_x \times \sigma_y} = \frac{\frac{1}{N} \sum (X-\bar{X})(Y-\bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum (X-\bar{X})^2} \times \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum (Y-\bar{Y})^2}}$$

Statistical analysis: Skeleton of analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Karl Pearson correlation coefficient were applied for statistical analysis.

Result and Discussion:

Seasonal incidence of mustard saw fly: From the result it was found that saw fly population was fluctuating during the whole cropping season (Table 1 and Fig. 1). Saw fly population was influenced by different weather parameters shown in (Table 2). Mustard saw fly seasonal incidence data (Table 1) revealed that the mustard saw fly appeared at an early seedling stage of crop i.e. from 46th (SMW) to 52th (SMW). The initial population of saw fly larvae (0.65 grub/plant) was first recorded during 3rd week of November 2024 (i.e. 46th SMW), and November increased 4th week of to (1.22 grub/plant) during 47th (SMW) when maximum temperature (27.5⁰C), minimum temperature (12.5⁰C), relative humidity morning (88.28 %), relative humidity evening (71.0%) and rainfall (0.02mm) was recorded. The maximum population (9.6 grub/plant) was recorded during 1st week of December 49th (SMW) with maximum temperature (26⁰C), minimum

temperature (9.9⁰C), relative humidity morning (82.0%), relative humidity evening (65.85%) and rainfall (0.0 mm).

Correlation coefficient between the occurrences of mustard saw fly with abiotic factor. The correlation coefficient of incidences of mustard saw fly on mustard crop with weather parameters revealed that the mustard saw fly population showed non-significant positive correlation with maximum temperature (0.0231) and negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.241) and relative humidity morning with negative correlation non-significant (0.0055), relative humidity evening and rainfall are positive correlation non-significant ($r= 0.0348$ & 0.0294) (Table 2).

Population fluctuation of mustard saw fly and Correlation with their weather parameters in mustard crop.

The occurrence of mustard saw fly appear at an early stage of crop growth in 46th SMW 46th (SMW) to 52 (SMW). The initial population as (0.65 grub/plant) was 1st recorded during 3rd week of November 2024 (46th SMW), 4th week of November increased to (1.22 grub/plant) during 47th (SMW) when maximum

temperature (27.5⁰C), minimum temperature (12.5⁰C), relative humidity morning (88.28 %), relative humidity evening (71.0%) and rainfall (0.02mm) was recorded. The maximum of 9.6 grub/plant was recorded during 1st week of December 49th (SMW) with maximum temperature (26⁰C), minimum temperature (9.9⁰C), relative humidity morning (82.0%), relative humidity evening (65.85%) and rainfall (0.0 mm) and correlation coefficient determining between the incidences of mustard saw fly on mustard crop with weather parameters revealed that the mustard saw fly population build up showed non-significant positive correlation with maximum temperature (0.0231) and negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.241) and relative humidity morning with negative correlation non-significant (0.0055), relative humidity evening and rainfall are positive correlation non-significant ($r= 0.0348$ and 0.0294).

This is in contrary with findings of Mishra (2018) who studied that mustard saw fly population was non-significant negative correlation with temperature, relative humidity and positive correlation with rainfall.

Table. 1. Population fluctuation of mustard saw fly (*Athelia lugens proxima*) in the relation with weather parameter during (Rabi 2024-25).

S. No.	SM W	Period	No of grub/plant	Temperature (°C)		Relative humidity (%)		RF (mm)
				Min.	Max.	Mor.	Eve.	
1	44	28/10/24 -03/11/2024	0 (1.0)	21.7	33.2	84.42	69.71	0.00
2	45	04/11/2024-10/11/2024	0 (1.0)	19.6	31.5	86.14	76.57	0.00
3	46	11/11/2024-17/11/2024	0.65 (1.28)	17.3	28.6	91.85	77.14	0.00
4	47	18/11/2024-24/11/2024	1.22(1.49)	12.5	27.5	88.28	71.0	0.02
5	48	25/11/2024-01/12/2024	2.63(1.90)	11.2	27.2	88.85	70.42	0.00
6	49	02/12/2024-08/12/2024	9.6(3.25)	9.9	26.0	82.0	65.85	0.00
7	50	09/12/2024-15/12/2024	3.16(2.04)	7.4	24.1	77.71	61.0	0.00
8	51	16/12/2024-22/12/2024	0.51(1.23)	7.8	25.5	85.71	67.28	0.00
9	52	23/12/2024-29/12/2024	0.12(1.06)	10.1	24.4	89.85	70.42	0.00
10	1	30/12/2024-06/01/2025	0.0(1.0)	10.5	18.8	86.57	76.71	0.00
11	2	07/01/2025-13/01/2025	0.0(1.0)	9.6	20.7	89.42	77.4	0.00
12	3	14/01/2025-20/01/2025	0.0(1.0)	11.4	20.7	88.7	73	0.00
13	4	21/01/2025-27/01/2025	0.0(1.0)	10.3	18.7	92.57	82.0	0.00
14	5	28/01/2025-03/02/2025	0.0(1.0)	9.1	24.7	94.0	64.0	0.00
15	6	04/02/2025-10/02/2025	0.0(1.0)	10.9	25.5	73.71	55.0	0.00

16	7	11/02/2025-17/02/2025	0.0(1.0)	11.3	26.4	75.42	51.4	0.00
17	8	18/02/2025-24/02/2025	0.0(1.0)	12.5	28.7	73.85	49.14	0.00
18	9	25/02/2025-03/03/2025	0.0(1.0)	13.8	29.0	72.85	49.85	0.00
19	10	04/03/2025-10/03/2025	0.0(1.0)	13.5	29.0	60.85	37.28	0.00

Table. 2. Correlation studies between mustard saw fly and weather parameters.

S. No	Meteorological Parameter	Correlation coefficient
1	Minimum temperature (°C)	-0.241
2	Maximum temperature (°C)	0.0231
3	Relative humidity (Morning) %	-0.0055
4	Relative (humidity Evening) %	0.0348
5	Rainfall (mm)	0.0294

Population of mustard saw fly and weather parameter in Rabi season 2024-25

Fig. 1. Seasonal incidence of mustard saw fly (*Athelia lugens proxima*) in their correlation with metrological parameter.

Table 3. Efficacy of chemical and botanical insecticide against mustard saw fly (*Athelia lugens proxima*) during Rabi season 2024-25.

Plots	Treatment Name	Dose /ha	Number of grub/plants (1 st Spray)				Mean 1 st spray	Number of grub/plants (1 st Spray)			Mean 2 nd spray	Over all mean 1 st + 2 nd spray
			DBS	3DAS	7DAS	10 DAS		3DAS	7DAS	10 DAS		
T1	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> 1.15% WP	5 kg	1.42 (1.56)	1.24 (1.50)	1.32 (1.52)	1.38 (1.54)	1.31	1.36 (1.54)	1.28 (1.51)	1.22 (1.49)	1.29	1.30
T2	Cyantraniliprole 10.26 OD	150 ml	1.27 (1.51)	1.22 (1.49)	1.3 (1.52)	1.35 (1.53)	1.29	1.32 (1.53)	1.26 (1.50)	1.18 (1.48)	1.25	1.27
T3	Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC	200 ml	0.88 (1.37)	0.62 (1.27)	0.41 (1.19)	0.21 (1.10)	0.41	0.19 (1.52)	0.39 (1.18)	0.59 (1.26)	0.39	0.40
T4	Lambda Cyhalothrin 2.5% EC	500 ml	1.44 (1.56)	0.8 (1.34)	0.83 (1.35)	0.87 (1.37)	0.83	0.85 (1.09)	0.81 (1.35)	0.79 (1.34)	0.82	0.83
T5	Flubendiamide 20 WG	100 ml	1.29 (1.51)	0.85 (1.36)	0.87 (1.37)	0.92 (1.39)	0.88	0.87 (1.37)	0.84 (1.36)	0.81 (1.35)	0.84	0.86
T6	Spinetoram 11.7% SC	200 ml	1.36 (1.53)	1.05 (1.43)	1.07 (1.44)	1.14 (1.46)	1.09	1.12 (1.46)	1.05 (1.43)	1.03 (1.43)	1.07	1.08
T7	Emamectin benzoate 5% SG	200ml	1.4 (1.55)	0.77 (1.33)	0.81 (1.35)	0.86 (1.37)	0.81	0.83 (1.35)	0.79 (1.34)	0.75 (1.32)	0.79	0.80
T8	Control		1.84 (1.69)	1.96 (1.72)	2.11 (1.76)	2.13 (1.77)	2.07	1.75 (1.66)	1.67 (1.63)	1.59 (1.61)	1.67	1.87
CD 5%			0.043	0.024	0.02	0.0118		0.022	0.014	0.026		
SE (m)			0.014	0.008	0.007	0.006		0.007	0.004	0.008		
SE(d)			0.02	0.011	0.009	0.008		0.01	0.006	0.012		
CV %			1.597	0.932	0.806	0.719		0.889	0.544	1.039		

Fig. 2. Bar diagram showing effects of insecticide against mustard saw fly (*Athelia lugens proxima*) after 1st spray.

Fig. 3. Bar diagram showing effects of insecticide against mustard saw fly (*Athelia lugens proxima*) after 2nd spray

Bio-efficacy of newer insecticides against mustard saw fly:

Pre-treatment:

The mean population of grub of mustard saw fly as per plant before treatment is given in (Table. 3 and Fig. 2). The observed data in the present study revealed that the infestation of grub mustard saw fly varies from 0.88-1.84 grub/ plant in different plot (that to be treated) including untreated plot and the difference between the treatment were not statistically significant, indicating that the population of mustard saw fly was spread more or less evenly in the field.

After first spray of chemical and botanical insecticides:

The data after first spray of insecticides are given in Table 3. Insecticides were applied in the mustard field two times, first after ETL Effectiveness of insecticides were observed after 3rd, 7th and 10th day after insecticide application at every spray.

Third day after 1st spray:

After third day after spray (DAS) data presented in Table 3, showed that all chemical

and bio-insecticidal treatment were significantly reduced the mustard saw fly (grub) population as compare to untreated plot (T8) (1.96 grub/plant). Among all the treatment (T3) Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC @200ml/ha insecticide was found significantly most effective treatment with lowest population (0.62 grub/plant), followed by (T7) Emamectin benzoate5% SG @200 ml (0.77grub/plant), (T4) Lambda cyhalothrin 2.5 % EC @500ml/ha (0.8grub/plant), (T5) Flubendiamide 20 WG@100ml/ha (0.85 grub/plant), (T6) Spinetoram 11.7% SC @200ml/ha (1.05 grub/plant), (T2) Cyantraniliprole 10.26 OD@150 ml/ha (1.22grub/plant), (T1) *Beauveria bassiana* 1.15% WP@5kg/ha (1.24 grub/plant) was recorded (Table 3 and Fig. 2).

Seven days after 1st spray:

Data after seven days of 1st spray is given in the Table 3. The result showed that all chemical and bio-insecticidal treatment substantially decreased population of mustard saw fly grub as compare with the (T8) (2.11 grub/plant). Among all the treatment (T3)

Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC @200ml/ha was found significantly most effective treatment with lowest population (0.41 grub/plant), followed by (T7) Emamectin benzoate 5%SG@200 ml (0.81 grub/plant), (T4) Lambda cyhalothrin 2.5 %EC @500ml/ha (0.83grub/plant), (T5) Flubendiamide 20 WG@100ml/ha (0.87 grub/plant), (T6) Spinetoram 11.7% SC @200ml/ha (1.07 grub/plant), (T2) Cyantraniliprole 10.26 OD @ 150 ml/ha (1.30 grub/plant), (T1) *Beauveria bassiana* 1.15% WP@5kg /ha (1.32 grub/plant) was recorded to be least effective treatment against mustard saw (Table. 3 and Fig. 2).

Ten days after 1st spray:

The data after ten days after 1st spray is shown in the Table. 3 The result showed that all the chemical and bio-insecticidal treatment significantly reduced the mustard saw fly population as compared to (T8) untreated plot (2.13 grub/plant). Among all the treatment (T3) Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC @200ml/ha insecticide was found significantly most effective treatment with lowest population (0.21 grub/plant), followed by (T7) Emamectin benzoate 5%SG@200 ml (0.86 grub/plant), (T4) Lambda cyhalothrin 2.5 %EC @500ml/ha (0.87grub/plant), (T5) Flubendiamide 20 WG@100ml/ha (0.92 grub/plant), (T6) Spinetoram 11.7% SC @200ml/ha (1.14 grub/plant), (T2) Cyantraniliprole 10.26 OD @ 150 ml/ha (1.35 grub/plant), (T1) *Beauveria bassiana* 1.15% WP@5kg /ha (1.38 grub/plant) was recorded than the untreated plot (Table 3 and Fig. 2).

Mean of 1st spray of chemical and bio-insecticide.

The mean of 1st spray of all insecticide revealed that the population of the mustard saw fly in the treated plots ranged between 0.41 grub/plant to 1.31 grub/plant and 2.07 grub/plant in the untreated plot (Table. 3). The treated plot showed a significant reduction in the pest population (T3) plot treated with Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC @200ml/ha was found significantly most effective treatment with lowest population (0.41 grub/plant),

followed by (T7) Emamectin benzoate 5%SG@200 ml (0.81 grub/plant), (T4) Lambda cyhalothrin 2.5 %EC @500ml/ha (0.83 grub/plant), (T5) Flubendiamide 20 WG@100ml/ha (0.88 grub/plant), (T6) Spinetoram 11.7% SC @200ml/ha (1.09 grub/plant), (T2) Cyantraniliprole 10.26 OD @ 150 ml/ha (1.29 grub/plant), (T1) *Beauveria bassiana* 1.15% WP@5kg/ha (1.31 grub/plant) was found least effective treatment against mustard saw fly, than the untreated plot (T8) (1.87 grub).

After second spray of insecticides.

The data of second spray of insecticides is shown in the (Table 3).

Third days after 2nd spray:

The data presented in (Table. 3 and Fig. 3), showed that all the chemical and bio-insecticidal treatments significantly reduced the mustard saw fly population as compared to (T8) untreated plot (1.75 grub/plant). Among all the treatment (T3) Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC @200ml/ha insecticide was found significantly most effective treatment with lowest population (0.19 grub/plant), followed by (T7) Emamectin benzoate 5%SG@200 ml (0.83 grub/plant), (T4) Lambda cyhalothrin 2.5 %EC @500ml/ha (0.85grub/plant), (T5) Flubendiamide 20 WG@100ml/ha (0.87 grub/plant), (T6) Spinetoram 11.7% SC @200ml/ha (1.12 grub/plant),(T2) Cyantraniliprole 10.26 OD @ 150 ml/ha (1.32 grub/plant), (T1) plot treated with *Beauveria bassiana* 1.15% WP@5kg /ha (1.36 grub/plant) showed least effective among all treatments.

Seven days after 2nd spray:

The result after seven days after 2nd spray showed that the all the chemical and bio-insecticidal treatment significantly reduced the mustard saw fly population as compare to (T8) untreated plot (1.67 grub/plant). Among all the treatment (T3) Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC @200ml/ha insecticide was found significantly most effective treatment with lowest population (0.39 grub/plant), followed by (T7) Emamectin benzoate 5%SG@200 ml (0.79

grub/plant), (T4) Lambda cyhalothrin 2.5 %EC @500ml/ha (0.81 grub/plant), (T5) Flubendiamide 20 WG@100ml/ha (0.84 grub/plant), (T6) Spinetoram 11.7% SC @200ml/ha (1.05 grub/plant), (T2) Cyantraniliprole 10.26 OD @ 150 ml/ha (1.26 grub/plant), (T1) *Beauveria bassiana* 1.15% WP@5kg /ha (1.28 grub/plant) was recorded to be least effective against mustard saw fly (Table 3 and Fig. 3).

Ten days after 2nd spray:

The data of ten days after 2nd spray is given in the (Table 3), proved that all the chemical and bio-insecticidal treatments substantially decreased mustard saw fly population as compared with the untreated plot (1.59 grub/plant). Among all the treatment (T3) Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC @200ml/ha insecticide was found significantly most effective treatment with lowest population (0.59 grub/plant), followed by (T7) Emamectin benzoate 5%SG@200 ml (0.75 grub/plant), (T4) Lambda cyhalothrin 2.5 %EC @500ml/ha (0.79 grub/plant), (T5) Flubendiamide 20 WG@100ml/ha (0.81 grub/plant), (T6) Spinetoram 11.7 % SC @ 200 ml/ha (1.03 grub/plant), (T2) Cyantraniliprole 10.26 OD @ 150 ml/ha (1.18 grub/plant), (T1) *Beauveria bassiana* 1.15% WP@5kg /ha (1.22 grub/plant) was recorded to be least effective against mustard saw fly (Table 3 and Fig. 3).

Mean of 2nd spray of insecticides.

The result of mean of second spray revealed that the population of mustard saw fly in treated plot ranged between 0.39 to 1.29 grub/plant and 1.67 grub/plant in untreated plot (Table 3 and Fig 3). The treated plot showed a significant reduction in the mustard saw fly population was (T3) Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC @200ml/ha insecticide was found significantly most effective treatment with lowest population (0.39 grub/plant), followed by (T7) Emamectin benzoate 5%SG@200 ml (0.79 grub/plant), (T4) Lambda cyhalothrin 2.5%EC @500ml/ha (0.82 grub/plant), (T5) Flubendiamide 20 WG@100ml/ha (0.84 grub/plant), (T6) Spinetoram 11.7% SC @200ml/ha (1.07 grub/plant), (T2)

Cyantraniliprole 10.26 OD @ 150 ml/ha (1.25 grub/plant), (T1) *Beauveria bassiana* 1.15% WP@5kg /ha (1.29 grub/plant).

Over all mean of both spray of chemical and bio- insecticide.

In untreated plot highest number of saw fly grub was found (1.87 grub/plant), whereas in chemical and bio-insecticidal treated plots mustard saw fly population was after both sprays. Among the all treatments, (T3) Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC @200ml/ha insecticide was found significantly most effective with lowest population (0.40 grub/plant), followed by (T7) Emamectin benzoate 5%SG@200 ml (0.80 grub/plant), (T4) Lambda cyhalothrin 2.5 %EC @500ml/ha (0.83 grub/plant), (T5) Flubendiamide 20 WG@100ml/ha (0.86 grub/plant), (T6) Spinetoram 11.7% SC @200ml/ha (1.08 grub/plant), (T2) Cyantraniliprole 10.26 OD @ 150 ml/ha (1.30 grub/plant) and (T1) *Beauveria bassiana* 1.15% WP@5kg /ha (1.27 grub/plant).

The finding of present study was similar to earlier studies done by Agarwal and Patel (2025), who reported that the chlorantraniliprole 18.50 SC was most effective insecticide in reducing the pest population of mustard saw fly and *Beauveria bassiana* was least effective against mustard saw fly. According to Vinyas, Neharkar and Matre (2022), Ghule and Bagged (2016) and Dhaka, Kumar and Pal (2020) lambda cyhalothrin was effective insecticide against mustard saw fly. According to Agrawal and Patel (2025) Cyantraniliprole 10.26 OD, Flubendiamide 20 WG, Spinetoram 11.7% SC are effective insecticide against mustard saw fly and Emamectin benzoate 5% SG was found effective against mustard saw fly according to (Dhaka, Kumar and Pal, 2020).

Summary and Conclusion:

Result of seasonal incidence of mustard saw fly showed first appearance of mustard sawfly (0.65 grub/plant) was observed at early seedling stage (i.e. 46th SMW) of the plant, and the highest incidence was observed at 49th

SMW i.e. 3rd week of November (9.6 grub/plant). Correlation study of mustard saw fly population with weather variable showed negative non-significant correlation with morning relative humidity ($r = -0.0055$) and positive non-significant correlation with evening relative humidity ($r = 0.0348$). Whereas, the negative correlation was found with minimum temperature and positive and non-significant correlation was found with maximum temperature ($r = -0.241$ and 0.0231), and rainfall ($r = 0.0294$) with mustard saw fly. Among seven insecticides used for efficacy, Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC was found to be most effective insecticide with minimum saw fly population (0.40 grub/plant) and *Beauveria bassiana* 1.5% WP was found lowest effectiveness against saw fly population (1.30 grub/plant).

Order of effectiveness of insecticides is Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC > Emamectin benzoate 5% SG > Lambda cyhalothrin 2.5% EC > Flubendiamide 20 WG > Spinetoram 11.7% SC > Cyantraniliprole 10.26 OD and *Beauveria bassiana* 1.15% WP was found least effective, while control plot have maximum number of grub (1.87 grub/ plant).

The highest cost benefit ratio was found with Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC @ 200 ml/ha (1:3.47). Hence it can be concluded from the present study that Chlorantraniliprole could be used as effective management tool in IPM programme with increasing economy of farmers.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgement: The authors are thankful to the Dr Saroj Chauhan, Assistant Professor Department of Entomology, Institute of Agriculture and Natural Sciences; and DDU Gorakhpur University Gorakhpur for providing all kind of assistance and help during this research work.

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